

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11193544>

SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A PILLAR OF THE ECONOMY

Sharobiddinov Ahrorbek Qosimjon ugli

3rd grade student of the Faculty of Economics of the Andijan Institute of Economics
and Construction

Abstract: *The main goal of the economic reforms of Uzbekistan is to build a strong democratic legal state and civil society with an open foreign policy, a stable socially oriented market economy. In the republic, market reforms are being carried out strictly and consistently. For this reason, many opportunities for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship are being created in our Republic. Small business and private entrepreneurship is an important factor in the development of the economy, increasing the employment and income of the population. This article discusses the concept of small business and entrepreneurship, the opportunities created for this activity, and the specific features of the industry.*

Key words: *small business, entrepreneurship, business, savings, economy, reform, law, commodity, service, property, finance, market.*

One of the main ways to strengthen the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, to develop it in all respects, and to speed up the transition of the economy, especially to the market relationship, is the development of small business and private entrepreneurship. Therefore, a number of laws, decrees and decisions dedicated to the development of entrepreneurship, its support by the state, initiative in private entrepreneurship, and its encouragement were adopted.

It is difficult to imagine the fundamental basis of the economic and social reforms being carried out in our country without entrepreneurship, factor and business qualities. The widespread development of free market relations is reflected in people's lives, their lifestyle, spiritual and life skills. Support of small business and private entrepreneurship ensures not only the continuous development of the economy, but also the economic goals related to the correction of economic relations, the development of competition and the filling of the consumer market.

The socio-economic development of our republic is based on market relations and is formed in ownership relations. The share of the non-state sector in social production is increasing, and small business and private entrepreneurship are growing rapidly. The president pays great attention to the development of small business and entrepreneurship.

Today, there are three types of business activity, according to which these groups of entrepreneurs can be specified separately:

1. Organization of a new product or service project. Owners of intellectual property are engaged in this type of business.

2. Entrepreneurs engaged in the organization of production of goods. The entrepreneur is engaged in the sale, resale and organization of commercial activities.

There are two types of entrepreneurship in terms of purpose:

a) aims to make a profit, achieve economic efficiency;

b) it is possible to show the types that aim to achieve social results (for example, nature protection, education of the young generation, health care). The specific characteristics of entrepreneurship are as follows:

possession of science, knowledge level in the field of work;

ability to take the initiative in making risk-based decisions;

ability to think deeply in economic processes;

effective use of laws;

putting innovations into practice;

striving for a goal;

organization;
to be thrifty, to go beyond one's word;
mentally pure and honest;
must be a selfless fighter for the team.

In conducting business activities, small business and private entrepreneurship are carried out through business. The word "business" is an English word, and it means business activity or the activity of people aimed at making a profit. The concepts of "entrepreneurship" and "business" in the economic activity of subjects of the market economy are close to each other, and in practice they can replace each other. In the dictionary of the Russian literary language, the word "businessman" is supposed to mean an entrepreneur, a worker, while "business" is understood as an activity, a profitable activity. Concepts such as "entrepreneur" and "businessman" mean a person engaged in production, brokerage, trade, financial and innovation activities and intending to earn income.

Today, our state provides financial assistance in the form of guarantees and compensation in order to provide financial support to small businesses and entrepreneurs. In 2020 alone, 33,208 billion received from commercial banks of 20,258 small businesses and entrepreneurs. 6,993 bln. by the state fund to support the development of business activities on loans of 6,993 soms. received financial obligations in the amount of soums. On the other hand, the results of the analysis show that in 2020: 4,172 billion of the fund will be provided to 5,356 small businesses and entrepreneurship entities on loans allocated by commercial banks. guarantee obligations in the amount of soums were received, as a result, the number of small businesses and business entities using the guarantee of the fund increased by 4.2 times compared to 2019; The number of small businesses and entrepreneurs who used the financial assistance of the fund in the form of compensation to cover the interest expenses on loans of commercial banks reached 14,902, and the fund provided 2,821 bln. took obligations for the compensation of interest expenses in the amount of soums,

as a result, the number of compensation recipients increased by 4.4 times and the amount of interest expenses to be paid by 3.3 times compared to 2019.

In addition, in order to strengthen the social protection of the population during the fight against the spread of the coronavirus infection and to ensure the stability of the economic sectors, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of 2020 No. PF-5969, PF-5978, PF-5986, PF-5996 in accordance with the decrees, the Fund provided financial support for the loans of about 6,000 small businesses and entrepreneurs.

As a result of the decisions made and the benefits given, the establishment of a set of private entrepreneurship and small business enterprises in Uzbekistan is progressing successfully. Enterprises engaged in small business activities independently of the state, that is, without large capital funds, can introduce workplaces, reduce the shortage of temporarily available goods, and even completely eliminate this shortage. possible

In the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, i.e., it is important to introduce new techniques, technologies, scientific achievements, and make economic changes in production and service. Since small business is one of the crucial sectors in the economy of our republic, the development of this sector is defined as one of the priority directions. For this reason, the government attaches great importance to the creation of a preferential legal framework for credit provision. In a word, the development of entrepreneurship and small business in our country remains one of the most priority areas of state policy today. In the words of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, we can achieve development and a prosperous life only through active entrepreneurship, tireless work and aspiration.

REFERENCES:

1. Рахматуллаева, Ф., & Шаробиддинов, А. (2023). YALPI HUDUDIY MAHSULOT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO ‘LLARI. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(S/4), 140-146.
2. Ergashev, I., & Sharobiddinov, A. (2023). IQTISODIYOTNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH SHAROITIDA BANK TIZIMINI ISLOH QILISH MASALALARI. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(4 Special Issue), 77-79.
3. O. T. Sattorqulov, B. B. Toshboev. O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning o'rni va ahamiyati. // *Yosh olim.* - 2015. - No 6 (86). - S. 455-458.